

Research Article

Solar Efficiency Accelerator using Mirror Systems (SEAMS)

Muhammed Sahal V A

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Muthoot Institute of Technology and Science, Varikoli P.O, Ernakulam, Kerala 682 308, India , sahalibnuabdullah@gmail.com

Anuja S

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Muthoot Institute of Technology and Science, Varikoli P.O, Ernakulam, Kerala 682 308, India , anujas1013@gmail.com

Adnan Razi

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Muthoot Institute of Technology and Science, Varikoli P.O, Ernakulam, Kerala 682 308, India , adnanraziknr@gmail.com

Aswin Lal K S

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Muthoot Institute of Technology and Science, Varikoli P.O, Ernakulam, Kerala 682 308, India, ksaswinlal@gmail.com

Dr. Chikku Abraham

Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Muthoot Institute of Technology and Science, Varikoli P.O, Ernakulam, Kerala 682 308, India, chikkuabraham@mgits.ac.in

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Abstract

The escalating global population has precipitated a corresponding surge in the demand for energy globally. Consequently, the imperative to shift from nonrenewable to renewable energy sources has become undeniable. Presently, solar panels are employed to harness solar radiation; however, their efficiency in utilising sunlight remains suboptimal. Our proposal SEAMS (Solar Efficiency Accelerator using Mirror System) advocates for the implementation of programmable mirror technology to maximise solar energy utilisation. This innovation facilitates precise focusing of sunlight onto the panels, thereby augmenting energy production and enhancing overall efficiency.

Key words - solar tracking, solar calculations, solar radiation, sunlight concentrating, mirror tracking, solar efficiency accelerator.

Introduction

The rapid growth of the global population has led to an unprecedented demand for energy, emphasizing the urgent need to transition to renewable sources. Among these, solar energy holds immense potential due to its abundance and sustainability. However, achieving optimal efficiency in solar energy harvesting remains a significant challenge.

Traditional solar tracking systems, such as single-axis and dual-axis trackers, have demonstrated improvements in energy capture by dynamically aligning solar panels with the sun's position. Despite their advantages, these systems often face limitations in efficiency due to suboptimal alignment and external environmental factors.

Recent advancements in solar concentrator technologies highlight the potential for programmable mirror systems to improve energy capture. For instance, hybrid-loop strategies and two-axis tracking designs have been proposed to enhance tracking precision. These approaches underscore the importance of real-time tracking and dynamic adjustments to optimize solar energy utilization.

The proposed SEAMS (Solar Efficiency Accelerator using Mirror System) leverages programmable mirror technology to overcome these limitations. By integrating real-time sun-tracking data with precise mirror adjustments, SEAMS ensures maximum solar energy capture. This innovative system addresses the inefficiencies of conventional trackers and offers a scalable solution for enhancing the performance of photovoltaic systems.

Expected Outcome

Time v/s Efficiency graph

To overcome space limitations and enhance solar panel efficiency, we propose integrating programmable mirror technology to redirect additional sunlight onto the panels. Assume that currently, panels receiving around 10 kWh of sunlight typically generate only 2–3 kWh of energy. By capturing and redirecting sunlight that would otherwise be wasted, this approach can significantly increase the amount of light absorbed, potentially boosting energy output to 5–6 kWh or more. This solution aims to maximize the effectiveness of existing installations without requiring additional space.

PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

SEAMS consists of three key mechanical structures: a single-axis solar stand, an LDR stand, and a mirror stand as shown in Fig 2. This paper analyzes SEAMS based on the provided flow and circuit diagrams, detailing component connections, functions, and operations.

Working parts of SEAMS

Flow Diagram

The Fig. 3 outlines the process of adjusting solar panel and mirror stands to optimise energy output. The major components in the flow are as follows:

Flow diagram of SEAMS

Key Components of the SEAMS System:

1. **LDR Stand**
2. **Microcontroller**
3. **Solar Panel Stand**
4. **Mirror Stand**

Circuit Diagram

Circuit Diagram

The circuit diagram provides a detailed view of the electronic connections and components involved in the solar tracker system.

The major components in the circuit are listed in Table I

Components Used in the SEAMS System

Component	Count	Description
Arduino UNO	1	Microcontroller: Processes signals from LDRs to control the solar panel and mirror positions.
LDRs	6	Sensors: Detect light intensity and send analog input to the microcontroller.
Servo Motors	6	Actuators: Adjust panel and mirror angles based on microcontroller signals.
Resistors	6	Passive components: Limit current to the LDRs.
Wires	Multiple	Connections: Link all components to the microcontroller.

3D Image of SEAMS

The Fig. 5 shown below combines the solar, mirror, and LDR stands, showing the full system in action. It highlights how the components work together to optimize solar energy capture and maximize efficiency throughout the day.

3D Image of SEAMS

Principle of Working

The Fig.6 shows how using a mirror to reflect additional sunlight onto a solar panel can increase the irradiance it receives. More irradiance means the panel captures more sunlight, which directly boosts its energy output. By reflecting sunlight at the correct angles, the mirror ensures the solar panel gets both direct and reflected sunlight. This technique enhances the efficiency of the solar panel, especially in scenarios where maximizing energy capture is essential. The more mirror stands we use in the SEAMS, the more output we will generate. It is easy to integrate more than one mirror stand with the SEAMS.

Working Principle

Solar Panel Stand

The solar panel stand is designed to optimise energy output by tracking the sun's movement using a single-axis rotation system powered by a servo or stepper motor. This system allows the panel to rotate and follow the sun's path across the sky, ensuring maximum exposure to sunlight.

Light-Tracking System

The light-tracking system uses two Light Dependent Resistors (LDRs) to detect the intensity of sunlight on both side of the panel. These LDRs are mounted on both side of the solar panel and are separated by small walls to avoid shadow interference.

LDR Setup

- **LDR A (Left Side):** Detects light intensity on the left side of the panel.
- **LDR B (Right Side):** Detects light intensity on the right side of the panel.

The primary function of the LDRs is to measure the light intensity difference between the left and right sides of the panel, providing input to the microcontroller.

Methodology

Reading Light Intensity

The microcontroller reads the voltage outputs from the two LDRs:

- $V_{LDR A}$: Voltage from LDR A.
- $V_{LDR B}$: Voltage from LDR B.

Calculating Light Intensity Difference

- The microcontroller calculates the difference in light intensity between the two LDRs:

$$\Delta V = V_{LDR A} - V_{LDR B}$$

- This difference (ΔV) determines the direction in which the panel needs to move to face the sun more directly.

Control Algorithm

The control algorithm operates as follows:

- **If $\Delta V > 0$:** LDR A is receiving more light than LDR B, indicating the sun is on the left side. The microcontroller signals the servo/stepper motor to rotate the panel to the left.
- **If $\Delta V < 0$:** LDR B is receiving more light than LDR A, indicating the sun is on the right side. The microcontroller signals the servo/stepper motor to rotate the panel to the right.

- **If $\Delta V = 0$:** Both LDRs are receiving equal light intensity, meaning the panel is already aligned with the sun. The microcontroller stops the motor.

Servo/Stepper Motor Movement

The servo/stepper motor is controlled by the microcontroller based on the calculated light intensity difference:

- The microcontroller sends precise control signals to the motor to adjust the panel's orientation.
- The motor rotates in small steps (if using a stepper motor) or precise angles (if using a servo motor), allowing for fine adjustments to the panel's position.

Real-Time Alignments of Solar Stand

Solar Stand Operations in Different Scenarios

Fig. 7 showcases the solar panel's alignment and performance at different times of the day (morning, noon, afternoon).

Mathematical Representation

Voltage Difference Calculation

The voltage difference between the two LDRs is calculated as:

$$\Delta V = V_{LDR A} - V_{LDR B}$$

Rotation Angle Calculation

The angle of rotation (θ) required to align the panel with the sun can be calculated based on the voltage difference and a scaling constant (K):

$$\theta = K \cdot \Delta V$$

Here, K is a constant that converts the voltage difference into an angle of rotation.

Real-Time Monitoring and Adjustment

The system continuously monitors light intensity on both sides of the panel and makes real-time adjustments to the panel's orientation. This ensures that the solar panel is always aligned to receive sunlight perpendicularly, maximizing energy output and efficiency.

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Continuous Monitoring

- The microcontroller reads the LDR voltages at regular intervals.
- It continuously calculates the voltage difference and adjusts the panel's position accordingly.

Maximizing Efficiency

- By aligning the solar panel perpendicular to the sun's rays, the stand maximizes energy output and efficiency.
- The real-time tracking mechanism ensures effective harnessing of solar energy.

Solar Panel Stand Working: Examples of Daily Operation

The solar panel stand adjusts throughout the day to maximize energy output by tracking the sun's movement. Below are examples of its operation during different times of the day:

Morning

- **Scenario:** Early morning, shortly after sunrise.
- **Sun Position:** Sun rises in the east.
- **Operation:**
 - o The left LDR detects more sunlight than the right LDR.
 - o The microcontroller moves the panel to the left to face the rising sun.

Noon

- **Scenario:** Midday, with the sun at its highest point.
- **Sun Position:** Directly overhead.
- **Operation:**
 - o Both LDRs receive similar sunlight intensity.
 - o The panel remains stationary, aligned perpendicularly to maximize energy capture.

Evening

- **Scenario:** Late afternoon, approaching sunset.
- **Sun Position:** Sun sets in the west.
- **Operation:**
 - o The right LDR detects more sunlight than the left LDR.

- o The microcontroller moves the panel to the right to face the setting sun.

Overview of Solar Stand

- Solar panel stand uses a light-tracking system with two LDRs.
- LDRs detect sunlight intensity on both sides of the panel.
- The microcontroller reads LDR outputs and calculates the light intensity difference.
- Controls a servo or stepper motor to adjust panel orientation.
- Aligns the panel perpendicular to the sun's rays for maximum energy output.
- Works with the LDR stand, both connected to the same microcontroller.
- Both systems operate independently to optimize solar energy harnessing.

LDR positioning on LDR Stand.

The arrangement detects light intensity differences between the four quadrants.

Working of Individual LDRs

Horizontal

- If LDR1 & LDR3 receive more light than LDR2 & LDR4, the light source is towards the left.
- If LDR2 & LDR4 receive more light than LDR1 & LDR3, the light source is towards the right.

Vertical

- If LDR3 & LDR4 receive more light than LDR1 & LDR2, the light source is towards the bottom.
- If LDR1 & LDR2 receive more light than LDR3 & LDR4, the light source is towards the top.

Movements of Servo Motors

Two servo motors are used for horizontal (X-axis) and vertical (Y-axis) movements.

Horizontal Movement (X-axis)

Difference Calculation:

$$\Delta X = V_{LDR1} - V_{LDR2} = V_{LDR3} - V_{LDR4}$$

Servo Position Calculation:

$$\theta_x = K_x \cdot \Delta X + \theta_0$$

Where K_x is a constant mapping the voltage difference to the servo angle, and θ_0 is the initial position of the servo.

LDR Stand

Detailed Working of Individual LDRs and Motor Movements

LDR Arrangement and Working

The LDRs are arranged in a cross pattern with small walls separating them to avoid shadow interference, as shown in Fig 8. This arrangement helps determine the direction of the light source more accurately.

- **LDR1:** Top-Left
- **LDR2:** Top-Right
- **LDR3:** Bottom-Left
- **LDR4:** Bottom-Right

Vertical Movement (Y-axis)

Difference Calculation:

$$\Delta Y = V_{LDR1} - V_{LDR3} = V_{LDR2} - V_{LDR4}$$

Servo Position Calculation:

$$\theta_Y = K_Y \cdot \Delta Y + \theta_0$$

Where K_Y is a constant mapping the voltage difference to the servo angle.

Real-Time Alignments of LDR Stand

The Fig.9 depicts the LDR-based light tracking system operating at different times of the day (morning, noon, afternoon).

LDR Stand Operations in Different Scenarios

Precise Description of Operation

1. **Initialization:** Initialize the LDRs and servo motors, setting them to the center position ($\theta_0 = 90^\circ$).
2. **Reading Light Intensity:** Measure the voltages from the LDRs: $V_{LDR1}, V_{LDR2}, V_{LDR3}, V_{LDR4}$.

3. **Calculating Differences:**

$$\Delta X = V_{LDR1} - V_{LDR2} = V_{LDR3} - V_{LDR4}$$

$$\Delta Y = V_{LDR1} - V_{LDR3} = V_{LDR2} - V_{LDR4}$$

4. **Mapping to Servo Positions:**

$$\theta_X = K_X \cdot \Delta X + \theta_0$$

$$\theta_Y = K_Y \cdot \Delta Y + \theta_0$$

5. **Moving Servos:** Adjust θ_X for ServoX and θ_Y for ServoY to point towards the maximum light intensity.

6. **Loop and Continuous Adjustment:** Continuously repeat the steps to track the light source.

Suppose the measured voltages are:

$$V_{LDR1} = 4V, \quad V_{LDR2} = 3V, \quad V_{LDR3} = 2V, \quad V_{LDR4} = 1V$$

Calculate the differences:

$$\Delta X = 2.0V, \quad \Delta Y = 1.0V$$

Assuming $K_X = 100$ and $K_Y = 25$:

$$\theta_X = 100 \cdot 2 + 90 = 290^\circ, \quad \theta_Y = 25 \cdot 1 + 90 = 115^\circ$$

Integration with Arduino

- The Arduino reads the voltages from each LDR through analog input pins.
- It calculates the voltage differences (ΔX and ΔY).
- Maps these differences to servo positions (θ_X and θ_Y).
- Sends control signals to the servos to adjust their angles accordingly.

Application to Solar Panel

- This setup determines the sun's position relative to a solar panel at a distance x from the LDR stand in terms of horizontal and vertical angles.
- Continuous tracking ensures the solar panel adjusts for maximum sunlight exposure, increasing efficiency.

Mirror Stand

The mirror stand plays a crucial role in maximizing solar panel efficiency by concentrating sunlight onto the panel. It achieves this through precise mirror adjustments using angle measurements from the LDR stand. Increasing the number of mirror stands in SEAMS further enhances the energy output of the solar panels.

Structure and Placement

The mirror stand is structurally similar to the LDR stand but replaces Light Dependent Resistors (LDRs) with mirrors. It is positioned south of the solar panel stand at a distance x , mirroring the LDR stand's placement to the north at the same distance. This symmetrical arrangement ensures smooth operation and accurate reflection.

Working Principle

1. Angle Measurement from LDR Stand

The LDR stand in SEAMS measures two critical angles:

- **Horizontal Angle (θ_{hor}):** Indicates the horizontal direction of the sun relative to the solar panel.
- **Vertical Angle (θ_{ver}):** Determines the vertical position of the sun relative to the solar panel.

2. Mirror Stand Adjustment

- **Horizontal Angle Adjustment:** When the microcontroller receives θ_{hor} from the LDR stand, it calculates the necessary horizontal motor movement. Example: For $\theta_{hor} = 30^\circ$, the microcontroller computes the motor adjustment required to align the mirrors for optimal sunlight reflection.
- **Vertical Angle Adjustment:** Similarly, the microcontroller processes θ_{ver} to determine the vertical motor movement. Example: For $\theta_{ver} = 15^\circ$, the microcontroller calculates the tilt adjustment for efficient sunlight capture.

Both θ_{ver} and θ_{hor} depend on the height and position of the mirror stand relative to the solar stand. These values vary with location and terrain.

3. Motor Operation

- **Direction:** Based on calculated adjustments:
 - Horizontal Adjustment: Motors move left or right to align the mirrors horizontally.
 - Vertical Adjustment: Motors move up or down to adjust the mirrors vertically.
- **Precision:** The microcontroller sends precise PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) or analog signals to the servo motors for continuous and accurate adjustment.

Integration with Microcontroller

The microcontroller continuously processes real-time angle data from the LDR stand. It translates these angle measurements into motor movements using trigonometric functions or specific mathematical equations. By integrating seamlessly with the mirror stand's servo motors, the microcontroller optimises the positioning of the mirrors throughout the day to maximise solar energy capture.

Real-Time Alignments of Mirror Stand

The Fig.10 illustrates the system's ability to concentrate sunlight effectively during morning, noon, and afternoon scenarios.

Mirror Stand Operations in Different Scenarios

Overview of Mirror Stand

- Improves solar panel efficiency by concentrating sunlight.
- Uses angle measurements from the LDR stand for dynamic adjustments.
- Enhances energy production and system efficiency.
- Scales effectively with the number of mirror stands in SEAMS.
- A key component in solar energy harnessing technologies.

Real-World Data Collection and Comparative Analysis

To validate the theoretical models outcomes discussed earlier, a practical data acquisition was carried out using a **10W photovoltaic module (Model: ASM-12010A)** manufactured by **Ammi Solar Pvt. Ltd.** This panel delivers a nominal power output of **10 Watts at 16.4 Volts** under standard test conditions (STC: 25°C, 100 mW/cm²). Manual measurements indicate that the solar panel operates at 15 percentage efficiency.

Experimental Setup

Three different configurations were used to measure and compare the solar panel performance:

1. **Static Panel Setup** (no tracking, fixed orientation)

2. **Single-Axis Tracking System** (horizontal/azimuth tracking)
3. **SEAMS-Enabled System** (dual-axis tracking with mirror-based sunlight concentration)

The solar panel was exposed to direct sunlight at different times of the day, and the **output voltage and current were measured** using a digital multimeter. The experiment was conducted under varying environmental conditions to analyze the variation in power output due to changes in **sunlight intensity, panel orientation, and ambient temperature**.

A plain mirror of the same size as the solar panel was used to concentrate additional solar irradiance onto the panel surface, enhancing its exposure to sunlight.

Environmental Conditions During the Observation Period

The TABLE V summarizes hourly ambient temperature and solar irradiance in the study area between 9:00 AM and 5:00 PM (IST), based on data collected from online sources such as *en.tutiempo.net* and *WeatherSpark*. These parameters are essential to understand solar panel performance relative to environmental factors.

Data Recording Methodology

- **Measurement Interval:** Hourly, from 7:30 AM to 6:30 PM
- **Measurement Tools:** Digital Multimeter.
- **Location:** Open outdoor environment with minimal shadowing
- **Reference Conditions:** Cloudy sky, average ambient temperature between 25–35°C
- **Mirror:** Multiple mirrors can enhance efficiency, here a single mirror setup is used for experimental simplicity.

Datas collected

Measurements of Solar Panel Parameters (Fixed Solar System)

Time	Voc (V)	Isc (A)	P (W)
07:30 AM	18.7	0.08	1.52
08:00 AM	19.4	0.18	3.6
08:30 AM	22.0	0.26	5.72
09:00 AM	21.0	0.28	5.88
09:30 AM	19.8	0.26	5.148
10:00 AM	20.2	0.46	9.292
10:30 AM	20.0	0.48	9.6
11:00 AM	20.1	0.6	12.06
11:30 AM	20.0	0.5	10.0
12:00 PM	19.7	0.48	9.456
12:30 PM	19.7	0.41	8.077
01:00 PM	19.4	0.32	6.208
01:30 PM	20.0	0.3	6.0
02:00 PM	19.7	0.23	4.531

Time	Voc (V)	Isc (A)	P (W)
02:30 PM	19.5	0.23	4.485
03:00 PM	19.4	0.18	3.492
03:30 PM	19.7	0.22	4.334
04:00 PM	19.6	0.25	4.9
04:30 PM	19.3	0.1	1.93
05:00 PM	18.7	0.06	1.122
05:30 PM	18.2	0.06	1.092
06:00 PM	17.1	0.02	0.342
06:30 PM	14.4	0.002	0.0288

Measurements of single axis Solar Panel Parameters

Time	Voc (V)	Isc (A)	P (W)
07:30 AM	18.7	0.12	2.3
08:00 AM	19.4	0.28	5.6
08:30 AM	20.0	0.4	8.0
09:00 AM	20.5	0.42	8.61
09:30 AM	20.1	0.32	6.432
10:00 AM	20.2	0.5	10.1
10:30 AM	20.1	0.5	10.05
11:00 AM	20.0	0.62	12.4
11:30 AM	20.1	0.5	10.05
12:00 PM	19.8	0.48	9.504
12:30 PM	19.8	0.44	8.712
01:00 PM	19.7	0.32	6.304
01:30 PM	20.0	0.31	6.2
02:00 PM	19.8	0.25	4.95
02:30 PM	19.5	0.23	4.485
03:00 PM	19.7	0.18	3.546
03:30 PM	20.0	0.25	5.0
04:00 PM	19.8	0.32	6.336
04:30 PM	19.5	0.11	2.145
05:00 PM	18.9	0.07	1.323
05:30 PM	18.4	0.06	1.104
06:00 PM	17.1	0.02	0.342
06:30 PM	14.4	0.002	0.0288

Measurements of Solar Panel Parameters(SEAMS enabled)

Time	Voc (V)	Isc (A)	P (W)
07:30 AM	18.7	0.15	2.93
08:00 AM	19.5	0.32	6.46
08:30 AM	20.0	0.43	8.6
09:00 AM	20.7	0.46	9.522
09:30 AM	20.5	0.37	7.585
10:00 AM	20.4	0.6	12.24
10:30 AM	20.3	0.57	11.571
11:00 AM	20.0	0.72	14.4
11:30 AM	20.4	0.6	12.24
12:00 PM	20.0	0.58	11.6
12:30 PM	20.0	0.5	10.0
01:00 PM	19.9	0.34	6.766
01:30 PM	20.0	0.31	6.2
02:00 PM	19.9	0.28	5.572
02:30 PM	19.6	0.23	4.508
03:00 PM	19.9	0.22	4.378
03:30 PM	20.2	0.28	5.656
04:00 PM	19.9	0.35	6.965
04:30 PM	19.6	0.12	2.352
05:00 PM	18.9	0.08	1.512
05:30 PM	18.4	0.07	1.288
06:00 PM	17.1	0.02	0.342
06:30 PM	14.4	0.002	0.0288

Hourly Ambient Temperature and Solar Irradiance (09:00 AM–05:00 PM IST)

Time (IST)	Temperature (°C)	Irradiance (W/m ²)
09:00 AM	29	670
10:00 AM	31	719
11:00 AM	33	889
12:00 PM	35	800
01:00 PM	34	714
02:00 PM	33	528
03:00 PM	31	174
04:00 PM	29	122
05:00 PM	27	52

Graph of Results

Fig. 11 illustrates the comparison of power outputs from three solar panel configurations: Normal (Fixed), Single Axis Tracking, and SEAMS (Mirror-Assisted). The SEAMS system consistently delivers higher power, particularly during peak irradiance hours between **10:00 AM** and **1:00 PM**, reaching up to **14.4 W**. Single Axis Tracking also shows improved performance over the fixed system throughout the day. The results highlight the effectiveness of tracking and reflective enhancements in maximizing solar energy capture under varying environmental conditions.

Output Data

Observations

The data clearly indicates that peak power output occurs around midday, particularly between 10:30 AM and 12:00 PM, when solar irradiance is highest and the panel receives more direct sunlight. During this period, the SEAMS system achieved a maximum power output of approximately 14.4 W.

W, which is around **15%** higher than the normal fixed system and the single-axis tracking setup. This confirms the advantage of optimal alignment and mirror-assisted concentration in maximizing energy capture.

When integrated with a single-axis tracking system, the solar panel exhibited a consistent improvement in performance over the fixed system, especially during the early and late hours of the day, where tracking helped maintain a favorable incidence angle. On average, the single-axis system delivered 10–15% more power than the fixed configuration throughout the observed period.

The SEAMS configuration outperformed both alternatives, particularly under high irradiance conditions, due to its combined use of dual-axis realignment and mirror-based sunlight redirection. However, in the early morning and late afternoon (e.g., 8:30 AM and after 4:30 PM), the performance gap between the systems narrowed, likely due to reduced solar intensity and ineffective angular concentration. Overall, the SEAMS system demonstrated a notable improvement in energy harvesting capability, validating its practical advantage for solar energy optimization.

Prototype Image

Advantages and Disadvantages

Advantages:

1. Increased energy production by focusing more sunlight onto panels.
2. Improved efficiency through optimal sunlight capture.
3. Space optimization, suitable for constrained areas.
4. Adaptability to various sunlight angles.
5. Scalability for small and large-scale applications.

Disadvantages:

1. High initial cost.
2. Maintenance requirements.
3. Technical complexity.
4. Weather dependence.

Conclusion

The SEAMS (Solar Efficiency Accelerator using Mirror System) demonstrates a promising advancement in solar energy harvesting by integrating programmable mirror technology with dual-axis tracking. Experimental results confirm that SEAMS significantly enhances power output compared to both static and single-axis tracking systems, achieving up to **62%** greater efficiency during pre peak irradiance hours such as 9 am. By concentrating and redirecting sunlight onto the panel surface, SEAMS effectively addresses limitations in conventional setups, particularly under high solar intensity conditions. This system not only improves energy conversion efficiency but also offers a viable solution to spatial and directional constraints in solar installations. Overall, SEAMS contributes meaningfully to the development of smarter, more sustainable solar technologies, paving the way for broader adoption in future renewable energy infrastructure.

Results and Discussion

The system uses a dual-axis tracking setup that relies on light sensors (LDRs) to detect the sun's position throughout the day. Based on the sensor readings, the mirrors adjust automatically to reflect and concentrate sunlight onto the solar panel. This continuous, real-time alignment helps the panel capture more sunlight than it would in a fixed position, leading to noticeably better energy output and overall efficiency.

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